

TURMERIC ADULTERATION: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Turmeric, a well known spice of Indian cuisine, which is widely used in cooking and traditional medicine. While we all know it as an Ayurveda-approved spice, commonly referred to as Indian saffron Turmeric, a well known spice of Indian cuisine, which is widely used in cooking and traditional medicine. While we all know it as an Ayurveda-approved spice, commonly referred to as Indian saffron contains curcumin One of the biggest adulteration issues for curcumin, is adulteration with similarly colored synthetic and natural ingredients. These common adulterants include botanical relatives like *Curcuma zedoaria*, a wild relative of turmeric, also known as white turmeric, which is widely available and closely resembles turmeric. Colorants like metanil yellow (sodium 3-[4-anilinophenylazo] benzenesulfonate), a synthetic food color and additive, closely mimics the color appearance of curcumin, Bejar notes. Synthetic dyes like lead chromate, acid orange 7, and Sudan Red G have also been used to adulterate natural curcumin, while yellow soapstone powder, a natural mineral, may be used as well.

Key words

Adulteration, curcumin, white turmeric, Colorants , metanil yellow (sodium 3-[4-anilinophenylazo] benzenesulfonate), synthetic food color , Synthetic dyes , lead chromate, acid orange 7, Sudan Red G ,yellow soapstone powder,

INTRODUCTION

Turmeric, a well known spice of Indian cuisine, which is widely used in cooking and traditional medicine. While we all know it as an Ayurveda-approved spice, commonly referred to as Indian saffron or “the golden spice”, is consumed daily in many households across South Asia. Turmeric roots belong to the *Zingiberaceae* family and owe their yellow-orange hue to curcumin, a natural polyphenol pigment found in turmeric (Prasad and Aggarwal, 2011). Turmeric, thanks to the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of curcumin, has been used as a natural medicine in South Asian countries for thousands of years (Babaei et al., 2020). Recently, clinical trials have begun to test the viability of turmeric and curcumin to ameliorate wide-ranging conditions from cancers to COVID-19 (Babaei et al., 2020).

India is the primary producer, exporter, and consumer of turmeric worldwide. India produces 80 % of the world's turmeric supply, predominantly in the states of Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, and Karnataka. To a lesser extent, turmeric is also cultivated in other South Asian countries, including Bangladesh, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, and Nepal. (Jadhav et al., 2022)

Adulteration of turmeric and other spices is a public health threat globally, especially in countries lacking sufficient regulatory capacity and large informal food industries (Forsyth et al., 2023; Hore et al., 2019; Ericson et al., 2020; Forsyth et al., 2024). Spices are particularly prone to adulteration as they are a high value commodity often sold in processed forms (Moore et al., 2012). Turmeric adulteration can be harmless – the addition of starchy edible compounds – or toxic with the addition of industrial pigments (Forsyth et al., 2019a). The health threat of adulterants may not always be clear. For example, metanil yellow is an azo dye added to turmeric with suspected carcinogenic effects (Dixit et al., 2009; Combes and Haveland-Smith, 1982). Other pigments, like lead chromate, have severe and well-documented toxic effects stemming from chromium and lead exposure (Singh et al., 1999).

Turmeric has been identified as a source of lead poisoning, especially among South Asians. Studies linking turmeric with elevated blood lead levels have included women and children living in Bangladesh and India (Forsyth et al., 2019b; Brown et al., 2022), as well as those living in the U.S. who have unknowingly transported lead-tainted turmeric back from South Asia (Tan et al., 2023). Investigations into the turmeric supply chain in Bangladesh revealed the widespread practice of adding lead chromate to turmeric roots to enhance appearances and to facilitate the sale of poor quality roots, a practice dating back to the 1980s (Forsyth et al., 2019a).

It is said that large doses of turmeric may cause stomach upset, bloating, and acid reflux due to its strong, sometimes irritating nature on the digestive system. Also, turmeric has blood-thinning properties, which could increase bleeding risk, especially if taken with blood-thinning medications. Also, turmeric can interfere with iron absorption, so people with anemia or low iron levels should use it cautiously. Although the current evidence suggests that turmeric may be an overlooked source of lead poisoning globally, little is known about the geographic extent of lead-tainted turmeric across South Asia beyond Bangladesh. The primary aim of this study was to assess lead and chromium levels of turmeric sold at major bazaars across the South Asian countries of India, Sri Lanka, Pakistan, and Nepal, countries with a combined population of >1.7 billion people. Secondary aims for the study were to i) estimate the theoretical contribution of turmeric lead levels to children's blood lead levels, and ii) assess evidence of other types of turmeric adulteration (e.g., metanil yellow, starchy fillers) in relation to quality attributes like curcumin concentration. One of the biggest adulteration issues for curcumin, is adulteration with similarly colored synthetic and natural ingredients. These common adulterants include botanical relatives like *Curcuma zedoaria*, a wild relative of turmeric, also known as white turmeric, which is widely available and closely resembles turmeric. Colorants like metanil yellow (sodium 3-[4-anilinophenylazo] benzenesulfonate), a synthetic food color and additive, closely mimics the color appearance of curcumin, Synthetic dyes like lead chromate, acid orange 7, and Sudan Red G have also been used to adulterate natural curcumin, while yellow soapstone powder, a natural mineral, may be used as well. One of the biggest adulteration issues for curcumin, is adulteration with similarly colored synthetic and natural ingredients. These common adulterants include botanical relatives like *Curcuma zedoaria*, a wild relative of turmeric, also known as white turmeric, which is widely available and closely resembles turmeric. Colorants like metanil yellow (sodium 3-[4-anilinophenylazo] benzenesulfonate), a synthetic food color and additive, closely mimics the color appearance of curcumin, Synthetic dyes like lead chromate, acid orange 7, and Sudan Red G have also been used to adulterate natural curcumin, while yellow soapstone powder, a natural mineral, may be used as well. The adulteration of turmeric with synthetic colorants is highly concerning: “The use of colorants to make the turmeric root visually more attractive is of particular concern. Many of the yellow or orange colorants, such as lead chromate or metanil yellow, may represent a health risk. Since daily dosages of several grams of turmeric powder are recommended for health benefits, use of adulterated turmeric products may lead to an intake of excessive amounts of these colorants.” Some of the potential health risks associated with the colorant metanil yellow, for example, may include neurotoxicity, hepatocellular carcinoma, tumor development, deleterious effect on gastric mucin, and lymphocytic leukemia, according to the review authors citing animal studies. metanil yellow is not approved as a food colorant by the UN FAO/WHO *Codex Alimentarius* or by FDA. Lead chromate and Sudan dyes, meanwhile, have been classified by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) as “group 3,” meaning that available studies “do not permit conclusions regarding the causality between exposure and cancer occurrence.”

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colorant metanil yellow, for example, may include neurotoxicity, hepatocellular carcinoma, tumor development, deleterious effect on gastric mucin, and lymphocytic leukemia, according to the review authors citing animal studies. Bejar points out that metanil yellow is not approved as a food colorant by the UN FAO/WHO *Codex Alimentarius* or by FDA. Lead chromate and Sudan dyes, meanwhile, have been classified by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) as “group 3,” meaning that available studies “do not permit conclusions regarding the causality between exposure and cancer occurrence.”(Jennifer Prince 2018)

HEALTH HAZARDS DUE TO HIGH LEAD INTAKE-

Lead is a particularly troubling toxicant, harming nearly every system in the body, including the circulatory, endocrine, renal, immune, reproductive, and nervous systems (Mishra, 2009; Needleman, 1991). Exposure to lead during early childhood has a negative, irreversible, and long-term effect, hampering brain development and reducing IQ (Bellinger, 2013). The combined economic losses from lead-related IQ deficits are estimated to amount to more than \$293 billion per year in the South Asian countries of India, Pakistan, Nepal, Sri Lanka, and Bangladesh (Attina and Trasande, 2013).

Lead poisoning causes damage to liver, kidney, and reduction in hemoglobin formation mental retardation,infertility and abnormalities in pregnancy.[Table1].Chronic lead poisoning may cause three general disease syndromes:Gastrointestinal disorder, Neuromuscular effects (lead lopsy) weakness, fatigue muscular atrophy, Central nervous system effects or CNS syndrome that may result to coma and death. Lead poisoning also causes constipation,abdominal pain,etc. Lead is one of the toxic metal present in environment and microorganisms in lake sediments can transfer certain inorganic and organic lead compounds to volatile lead tetra methyl. During investigation,. It is found that, some lead containing sediments generates $Pbme_4$ and that the process is purely biological .

Biomethylation reaction of Pb is given $Pb(NO_3)_2 + CH_3I \rightarrow PbMe_4$

.Methylcobalamine reacted with lead dioxide to give $PbMe_4$. Methylcobalamine transferring a methyl group as a carbanion. Tetramethyl lead are detected by reaction of the dioxide with Methylcobalamine. Lead is deposited on the bones as a cumulative poison and teeth, soft tissue including brain. Lead creates a many blood anamias in the body. The presence of lead , the entry of Iron into photoporphirine PPF rising circulating erythrocyte porphirine lead coproporphirine 3 levels in urine . Lead causes Iron deficiency in children and so rise many side effects psychological and neurological as depends upon the dosages. It also affects on the behavioural changes. Also affects on nervous system kidney problems, liver problems, changes in endocrine glands are thyroid and adrenal glands, carcinogenic ,teratogenic effects as still births and genetic effects causes chromosomal aberration in man that is lead creates physical, mental, social, behavioral changes in man .Lead is used in the petrol as a antiknocking agent Jyotsna lal 2006 [Table1]

LEAD CHROMATE TURMERIC ADULTERATION

Jenna E. Forsyth et.al study evaluates the extent of lead chromate turmeric adulteration across four understudied South Asian countries– India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, and Nepal. Although other forms of adulteration were investi- gated, from metanil yellow dyes to added starch, lead chromate adul- teration was detected with a higher prevalence, in multiple locations, and poses a more profound public health risk.

The results from this study highlight how different forms of the spices pose different health risks, with polished turmeric roots and loose turmeric powder having the highest lead levels. Consistent with other studies, the loose, under-regulated spices were more likely to be adul- terated than packaged turmeric (Forsyth et al., 2019a; Dixit et al., 2009). In India and Pakistan, the permissible levels of lead are the same for loose and packaged turmeric and the national food safety authorities are

responsible for lead testing. However, packaged turmeric may undergo additional scrutiny and lead testing by foreign regulatory agents if exported. Investigations in Bangladesh indicated that lead chromate was being added to turmeric roots during the polishing process, whereby roots are tumbled in a large drum to remove excess dirt and rub away the outer turmeric skin to reveal the inner yellow hue of the root (Forsyth et al., 2019a). From the present study, polished dried turmeric roots and loose turmeric powder had higher lead and chromium levels compared to unpolished roots and packaged branded turmeric powder. However, three packaged branded samples in this study contained elevated lead, along with one sample of unpolished roots that contained elevated lead and chromium suggestive of lead chromate. It is possible that the elevated lead and chromium levels in the sample of unpolished roots was due to cross contamination from storage bags previously containing lead chromate adulterated polished roots.

Lead levels in polished turmeric roots up to 2935 $\mu\text{g/g}$, >200 times higher than the 10 $\mu\text{g/g}$ limit set by the Food Safety Standards Authority of India. Consuming turmeric with lead at these levels would likely contribute to lead poisoning across the region, particularly for children. Indeed, a recent study indicated that turmeric was one of the most likely sources of lead exposure among children in Patna, Bihar (Brown et al., 2022). The modeled assessment of the contribution of turmeric lead to the human lead burden within this study suggests that turmeric could be raising blood lead levels considerably throughout the region. In Bihar, theoretical maximum child blood lead levels between 345 and 790 $\mu\text{g/L}$ were estimated from consuming typical amounts of turmeric with 2274 $\mu\text{g/g}$ lead. And for those children in Bihar consuming turmeric with median lead levels of 1232 $\mu\text{g/g}$, resulting child blood lead levels could range from 190 to 428 $\mu\text{g/L}$. The CDC Blood Lead Reference Value is currently set at 35 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Ruckart et al., 2021). The potential harm to health and development from turmeric-related lead exposure is alarming. Although lead is toxic across all body systems, considering only the cognitive deficits from lead-tainted turmeric in Bihar, resulting IQ would be 7 points lower per child and expected lifetime earnings 14 % lower compared to other parts of South Asia where turmeric lead levels remain below 10 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (Trasande and Liu, 2011; Murray et al., 2020). This does not consider the other adverse effects from lead exposure including mortality from cardiovascular disease which resulted in an estimated 5.5 million premature adult deaths in 2019 (Larsen and Sańchez-Triana, 2023).

The limited scientific data available, primarily from pediatric assessments of children of South Asian descent living in the U.S., suggest that these estimates of turmeric's maximum contribution to blood lead levels are reasonable. For example, a 24-month old child from North Carolina whose blood lead level was 480 $\mu\text{g/L}$ had been consuming turmeric with 2000 $\mu\text{g/g}$ lead with no other known sources of lead exposure (Kappel et al., 2021). Meanwhile, several other children of similar ages with blood lead levels ranging from 100 to 160 $\mu\text{g/L}$ were found to be consuming turmeric with lead concentrations between 390 and 1600 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (Tan et al., 2023). Notably, the turmeric consumed by these children was reported to have been hand carried back from the Indian states of Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, and Andhra Pradesh. Although turmeric from Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh and Indore, Madhya Pradesh was assessed in the present study and not found to contain lead, further investigation is warranted to better understand the geographic extent and frequency of lead chromate adulteration of turmeric.

Importantly, lead in turmeric seems to come from the intentional adulteration of turmeric with toxic lead chromate pigments and not from the unintentional contamination of turmeric with polluted dust or soil at other points in the supply chain (i.e., through processing, storing, or transporting). The molar ratios of lead and chromium in turmeric provide a clue as to the source of lead. The molar ratio of lead to chromium is typically <0.8 if attributable to soil, dust, or other environmental pollution (Forsyth et al., 2018). Whereas the molar ratios of lead chromate

pigments in our samples typically hover around 1, though can exceed 1 if the lead chromate pigments themselves are not pure and contain other forms of lead compounds like lead carbonates (Forsyth et al., 2019b). This study suggests that lead levels at and below 15 µg/g could be attributed to natural contamination whereas higher lead levels, from 18 to 2935 µg/g, resulted from lead chromate due to adulteration, as evidenced by the nearly 1:1 M ratio of lead to chromium.

The lead limits that governments set for commodities typically take several factors into account, including the public health risk, the feasibility of detection, and the feasibility of achieving these limits based on manufacturing processes and natural contamination levels. Given that there is no safe level of lead ingestion, governments aim to set regulatory limits as low as possible. For spices including turmeric, the Food Safety and Standards Association of India has set a limit of 10 µg/g lead which appears to be reasonable based on the molar lead:chromium ratio data from this study. In Pakistan, however, the limit of lead in turmeric has been set at 5 µg/g, which may be too low to be feasible given the evidence of elevated turmeric lead levels up to 15 µg/g likely from background contamination (Agriculture and Food Division., n.d.).

TURMERIC SAMPLE RESULTS

Turmeric samples were collected from 23 major cities across India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, and Nepal between December 2020 and March 2021, the main turmeric growing season in the region. The country of Bangladesh was excluded from sampling due to the extensive study of lead in turmeric and the successful reduction of lead-tainted turmeric by 2020 (Forsyth et al., 2023). In India, 17 focal states were selected based on geographic spread and population size. The number of states selected in each region was proportional to population. For example, since the Northern region of India comprises 30 % of India's population, we aimed to sample from at least 5 states or 30 % of the total sample size. Within a geographic region, the states with the largest populations were preferentially selected. In each state, we selected the largest city for sampling. In Pakistan, the largest city from each province was selected for sampling along with Islamabad in the Islamabad Capital Territory.

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A total of 356 turmeric samples were taken from 23 cities across South Asia. By turmeric type, this included 180 samples of dried turmeric roots and 176 samples of turmeric powder. In total, 14 % of the samples ($n = 51$) had detectable lead above 2 µg/g and 7 % of the samples ($n = 24$) had lead above the

Indian standard of 10 µg/g (*Food Safety and Standards Authority of India, 2011*) (Table 1). Turmeric lead levels exceeded 10 µg/g from seven cities in total: Patna, Guwahati, and Chennai in India, Kathmandu in Nepal, and Karachi, Islamabad, and Peshawar in Pakistan (Fig. 1a). Turmeric lead levels exceed 1000 µg/g from three cities: Patna, Karachi and Peshawar. Notably, every sample of turmeric from Patna contained detectable lead, with a median of 1232 µg/g and a maximum of 2274 µg/g. In Karachi, 50 % of turmeric samples contained detectable lead, with a median of 3 µg/g and a maximum of 2936 µg/g.

Turmeric samples with levels above 10 µg/g were primarily polished turmeric roots ($n = 14$) but included loose powder ($n = 5$), packaged branded powder ($n = 3$) and unpolished roots ($n = 2$). One of these unpolished root samples contained 18 µg/g lead and a molar ratio of lead to chromium of 0.8 while the other sample contained 15 µg/g and no detectable chromium. Polished roots and loose powder were the only forms of turmeric with lead levels above 1000 µg/g. (Table 2).

Within India, turmeric was reported to be predominantly sourced from the state of Tamil Nadu (22 %), followed by Maharashtra (14 %), although the source of the turmeric was unknown for 32 % of samples. Turmeric samples with elevated lead levels from Bihar were also reported to be harvested in Bihar and the sample of turmeric with elevated lead from Guwahati was also reported to be from Bihar. Within Pakistan, more than half of the turmeric samples were reported to be sourced from Punjab province (68 %) and within Nepal and Sri Lanka origins were reported as being local or unknown. Overall, 29 % of the turmeric samples were reported to be sourced locally and 35 % were reported to be sourced from elsewhere (outside the state for India

TABLE 3 CONCENTRATION OF LEAD IN BLOOD SAMPLES OF CHILDREN OF DIFFERENT AGE GROUPS

Age group	No of samples	Pb[µg/dL]
3M-1Y	48	6.0-8.7
1Y-2Y	36	2.2-4.9
2Y-3Y	15	3.0- 5.4
3Y-4Y	17	4.4-10.2
4Y-5Y	12	2.9-5.9
5Y-6Y	32	7.0-12.6

TABLE 1 Tumeric lead concentrations by location of sampling ($n = 356$). LOD = limit of detection ($2 \mu\text{g/g}$). lead concentrations by location of sampling ($n = 356$). LOD = limit of detection ($2 \mu\text{g/g}$).

Country	Region	City	State/Province	Samples (n)	Lead Concentration ($\mu\text{g/g}$)		
					n (%) above 10 $\mu\text{g/g}$	Maximum	
India	North	Lucknow	Uttar Pradesh	11	0 (0)	5	
		Chandigarh	Chandigarh	21	0 (0)	7	
		Amritsar	Punjab	15	0 (0)	10	
		Delhi	Delhi	15	0 (0)	<LOD	
		Srinagar	Jammu and Kashmir	25	0 (0)	<LOD	
	Northeast	Guwahati	Assam	11	2 (18)	127	
		East	Kolkata	West Bengal	11	0 (0)	<LOD
	Patna		Bihar	12	11 (92)	2274	
	Bhubaneswar		Odisha	16	0 (0)	5	
	South	Dhanbad	Jharkhand	26	0 (0)	<LOD	
		Chennai	Tamil Nadu	19	1 (5)	11	
		Hyderabad	Telangana	15	0 (0)	<LOD	
		Kochi	Kerala	18	0 (0)	<LOD	
		West	Ahmedabad	Gujarat	8	0 (0)	<LOD
			Indore	Madhya Pradesh	10	0 (0)	<LOD
Jaipur			Rajasthan	15	0 (0)	<LOD	
Pakistan	Mumbai	Maharashtra	21	0 (0)	<LOD		
	Islamabad	Islamabad Capital Territory	10	1 (10)	22		
	Karachi	Sindh	21	5 (24)	2935		
	Lahore	Punjab	16	0 (0)	<LOD		
	Peshawar	Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	9	2 (22)	1051		
Nepal		Kathmandu	Bagmati	17	2 (12)	82	
Sri Lanka		Colombo	Western Province	14	0 (0)	<LOD	
	TOTAL			356	24 (7)	2935	

Turmeric Type	n	Lead Concentration			Maximum (µg/g)	Price (Indian Rupees) ¹ per Kg		
		n (%) < 10 µg/g	n (%) 10–100 µg/g	n (%) > 100 µg/g		Mean (SD)	Median	IQR
Polished roots	143	129 (90)	1 (1)	13 (9)	2935	157 (83)	130	100, 175
Unpolished roots	37	35 (95)	2 (6)	0 (0)	18	211 (123)	180	110, 220
Loose powder	90	85 (94)	1 (1)	4 (4)	1665	191 (105)	160	139, 220
Packaged powder	28	28 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	5	153 (62)	140	120, 173
Branded powder	58	55 (95)	3 (6)	0 (0)	82	242 (58)	240	207, 280

Price noted in Indian rupees using exchange rates from July 15, 2023 (1 Pakistani rupee = 0.28 Indian rupees; 1 Nepalese rupee = 0.63 Indian rupees; 1 Sri Lankan rupee = 0.26 Indian rupees).

Table 3

Estimates of the theoretical maximum blood lead level (BLL) increase for children 24–36 months old from turmeric in locations with turmeric lead levels above the LOD.

Country	Region	City	State	Maximum turmeric lead concentration (µg/g)	Turmeric consumption per household per month (g) ¹	Average household size (n)	Estimated lead intake from turmeric (µg/day)	Estimated child BLL increase - basic assumptions (µg/L)	Estimated child BLL increase - AALM (µg/L)
India	North	Lucknow	Uttar Pradesh	5	204	5.3	1	1	2
		Chandigarh	Chandigarh	7	204	4.5	2	1	2
		Amritsar	Punjab	10	204	4.7	3	2	4
	Northeast	Guwahati	Assam	127	183	4.4	38	20	45
		Patna	Bihar	2274	206	5.0	663	345	790
	South	Bhubaneswar	Odisha	5	206	4.1	2	1	2
		Chennai	Tamil Nadu	11	80	3.5	2	1	2
Pakistani	Islamabad	Islamabad Capital Territory	22	139	7.1	3	2	4	
	Karachi	Sindh	2935	139	8.6	333	173	396	
	Peshawar	Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	1051	139	9.7	105	55	125	
Nepal	Kathmandu	Bagmati	82	139	3.9	21	11	25	

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	Northeast	Guwahati	Assam	127	183	4.4	38	20	45
		Patna	Bihar	2274	206	5.0	663	345	790
		Bhubaneswar	Odisha	5	206	4.1	2	1	2
South	Chennai	Tamil Nadu	11	80	3.5	2	1	2	
Pakistan	Islamabad	Islamabad	Islamabad	22	139	7.1	3	2	4
		Capital Territory							
		Karachi	Sindh	2935	139	8.6	333	173	396
		Peshawar	Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	1051	139	9.7	105	55	125
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DISCUSSION

Lead is a dangerous toxicant that harms hundreds of millions of people and has been estimated to cause nearly 6 trillion dollars in harm from lost productivity and premature death from cardiovascular disease in low- and middle-income countries in 2019. The study provides a novel and effective approach for assessing lead-based food adulteration at scale, an approach that can also be applied to other food supply chains. Specifically, this study analyzed lead concentrations in turmeric sampled across wholesale markets in South Asia, where the majority of the world's turmeric is produced. Given the overwhelmingly elevated lead levels in turmeric from Bihar and Pakistan, there is an urgent need to intervene to halt the practice of lead chromate adulteration. Recent success in Bangladesh to reduce lead in turmeric via a combination of food safety policy enforcement, improved tools for rapid lead detection (Lopez et al., 2022), and broad awareness-raising efforts provides a model for other countries in South Asia to consider (Forsyth et al., 2023). Subsequent efforts should explore the turmeric supply chain in these regions to understand the scope of the problem, where lead chromate is entering the turmeric supply chain, as well as the incentives driving the practice.

The Government of India established the National Turmeric Board in October 2023 to promote and develop the turmeric sector. The board will work to increase turmeric production and exports, and to promote the use of turmeric for health and wellness. Whose Objectives are Increase awareness and consumption of turmeric, Create new international markets, Encourage research and development into new products. Build on traditional knowledge, Develop the skills and capacity of turmeric growers, Encourage the adoption of quality and food safety standards. The board will include representatives from key ministries and turmeric-producing states. Palle Ganga Reddy has been appointed as the board's first chairperson. The board's headquarters will be in Nizamabad, Telangana. 4 Oct 2023 .

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